

Patient Satisfaction Index Using the Indonesia Health Card (Kis) in Services in Hospital Inpatient Installations

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Abstract:- Background: In the current era of globalization, of course, everyone can determine where they will choose health services, with the progress of the times and the sophistication of technology in health equipment, people have become aware of what is best for them to do in undergoing treatment, this proves that when undergoing treatment hope to always be served well. **Objective:** Know the satisfaction index. **Patients using Indonesia Health Cards (KIS) in health services. Method:** This research uses descriptive quantitative, data processing is guided by KEMENPAN No. Kep/25/M.PAN2/2004. samples were taken based on chance. The research period is October-November 2023. With a sample size of 150 respondents. **Results:** characteristics of respondents: age 80.7% early adulthood 26-35 years, gender 74.7% female, education 76.7% high school, occupation 70% self-employed. The average value of the quality index for each service element is 2.44, the lowest is service speed and the highest value is 2.84 for service procedures. The satisfaction index value where the average value per element is converted to a basic value of 25, then the index value obtained is 62.75, so it can be interpreted that the service performance is of good quality **Suggestion:** continue to do your best for patients and the company you work for even if the service is considered satisfactory because always giving your best can result in a faster recovery for the patient.

Keywords:- Satisfaction Index, Health Services.

I. INTRODUCTION

Health development is part of national development to realize the president's vision and mission and implement the fifth Nawacita to improve the quality of life of Indonesian people in the era of globalization (Permenkes, 2016).

In the current era of globalization, people's needs for health services have changed to become higher quality. With the increase in the level of education and socio-economic conditions of the population, the public's demands for the quality of health services are important components that cannot be separated from each other, with the indication that society is increasingly critical in demanding excellent service, (Nursalam, 2014).

Excellent service is a translation term from the words "excellent service" which means the best or very good service. It is called the best or very good because it meets current service standards or is owned by an agency that provides services that can provide patient satisfaction (Arista, 2018).

Patient satisfaction is an opinion and assessment of the quality of health services received by patients. Patients feel satisfied if the results of the services provided match or even exceed their expectations (Permenkes, 2022).

Nursing services are companies that, with their knowledge, will and ability, help people, both sick and healthy, from birth to death, especially with the development of knowledge (Yulihastin, 2009).

Advances in science and technology influence changes in health services. On the one hand, this provides many benefits, namely increasing the quality of service as reflected in indicators of reducing morbidity, disability, and death and increasing average life expectancy. Changes like health care may become more apparent when it is recognized that a variety of high-tech devices are now widely used.. (Mubarak, 2009).

The results of Suzana's (2023) research on the community satisfaction index at the Hasanudin Damra Manna General Hospital, Bengkulu, where the service elements provided had a conversion result of 76.48 in service quality B with the good category.

From the description above, researchers are interested in taking the research title Patient Satisfaction Index for Healthy Indonesia Card Users (KIS) in services at Hospital Inpatient installations.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is research with a quantitative descriptive design. This method starts with collecting data, analyzing the data and interpreting it. The population of this study were all patients using Indonesian Health Cards who were hospitalized, samples were taken based on chance, if patients were found according to the researchers' criteria then they were used as samples, while the samples in the study were to meet the accuracy of the results of the

satisfaction index based on the formula (Number of elements + 1) X 10 = number of respondents. 14+1x10 = 150. So the sample in this research consisted of 150 respondents.

The sample in this research was based on the researcher's reasoning with the criteria, namely that the respondent was at least early adulthood, the respondent was cooperative, willing to be a respondent and registered as a KIS user participant with the research being conducted from October to November 2023.

➤ *Research Ethics*

The researcher prepared informed consent first before conducting the research, when in the field the researcher asked the staff in the room whether the patient was a KIS user, then the researcher approached the respondent introduced himself and explained the aims and objectives of the researcher. If the respondent was willing, he was asked to sign the sheet he had made and explain how to protect it. confidentiality.

➤ *Data processing techniques*

The results of filling in the questionnaire are checked, then data processing is carried out which is guided by the preparation of the Community Satisfaction Index (IKM)

according to the Minister of State for Administrative Reform, hereinafter abbreviated as (KEMENPAN) No. Kep/25/M.PAN2/2004 as follows:

Calculate the average value (NRR) for each indicator using the following formula:

$$NRR = \frac{\text{Total Perception Value of Indicators}}{\text{Number of Respondents}}$$

Calculate the weighting value for all indicators using the formula:

Weighing value =

Then calculate the weighted average value (NRR) using the formula: weighted NRR = NRR x weighted value. Next, to find out the community satisfaction index (IKM) using the service unit IKM, the sum of the weighted NRR for each indicator is interpreted and converted to a base value of 25, more specifically as follows: service unit IKM = \sum weighted NRR for each indicator x 25. After that, to find out the NRR value and IKM refer to the table below:

Table 1 Interpretation of NRR and IKM

NRR	IKM	Service Quality	Service Unit Performance
1,00 – 1,75	25 – 43,75	D	Not good
1,76 – 2,50	43,76 – 62,50	C	Half good
2,51 – 3,25	62,51 – 81,25	B	Good
3,26 – 4,00	81,26 – 100,00	A	Very good

➤ *Data processing device*

Data entry is carried out using a computer program by filling in the form starting from element 1 to element 14, the value of each service element is added up (down) then the total value of each element is divided by the number of respondents who filled in, then to get the average value weighted then the average value per service element is multiplied by 0.071 as the weighted average weight value.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Univariate Analysis*

Statistical analysis test of the frequency distribution of characteristics of respondents using Indonesian Health Cards in hospital services is as follows:

- *Characteristics of respondents who use Indonesian Health Cards in services at hospital inpatient installations*

Research results regarding the characteristics of respondents, age, gender, education and employment in feeling service satisfaction. For more details, it is described in the table as follows:

Table 2 Distribution of characteristics of patients using the Healthy Indonesia Card according to age, gender, education and occupation in hospital inpatient installations in 2023 (n=150)

No	Characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percent (%)
1	Age	Late teens 17-25 years old	0	0
		Early adulthood 26-35 years	121	80,7
		Late adulthood 36-45 years	27	18
		Elderly 46-55 years	2	1,3
2	Gender	1. Boy	38	25,3
		2. Female	112	74,7
3	Education	1. Elementary School	6	4
		2. Junior High School	10	6,7
		3. High school	115	76,7
		4. Diplomas	5	3,3
		5. Bachelor	14	9,3
4	Work	1. Government employees	5	3,3
		2. Private Employees	40	26,7
		3. Entrepreneur	105	70

From Table 1 above, it can be interpreted that the characteristics of respondents who use Indonesian Health Cards are the largest age, 80.7%, early adults, 26-35 years, the largest gender, 74.7% female, and the highest secondary school education, 76.7%, while for occupation most 70% are self-employed.

- Know the description of the quality index for the service elements for patients using Indonesian Health Cards regarding the service elements in the Hospital Inpatient Installation.

This research looks at the average value per element of service to patients. For more clarity, see the table as follows:

Table 3 Quality Value Per Element of Hospital Inpatient Installation Services

No	Service elements	Average value per Element	Quality	Performance
1	Service Procedures	2,84	B	Good
2	Terms of Service	2,69	B	Good
3	Clarity of Service Officers	2,51	B	Good
4	Discipline of service officers	2,52	B	Good
5	Officer Responsibilities	2,53	B	Good
6	Service Personnel Capabilities	2,77	B	Good
7	Speed of Service	2,44	C	Not good
8	Justice in Getting Services	2,58	B	Good
9	Politeness and Friendliness of Officers	2,53	B	Good
10	Reasonable Service Fees	2,57	B	Good
11	Certainty of Service Fees	2,56	B	Good
12	Certainty of Service Time Schedule	2,59	B	Good
13	Environmental Comfort	2,54	B	Good
14	Service Security	2,63	B	Good

Table 2 shows that of all the elements of inpatient services, the lowest average value for each element of service is speed of service, 2.44, which is perceived as poor by patients using Indonesian Health Cards. The highest element is 2.84 elements of service procedures with good performance.

- The description of the patient satisfaction index for Indonesian Health Card users regarding the performance of hospital inpatient installation services is as follows:

Table 4 Description of the patient satisfaction index for Healthy Indonesia Card users regarding the performance of hospital inpatient installation services

No	Installation	Indeks	Quality	Performance
1	Inpatient Installation	62.75	B	Good

Table 3 shows the satisfaction of patients using Indonesian Health Cards in inpatient settings from all service elements in the nursing services provided with an index of 62.75, good nursing service performance with quality B (Good).

❖ Discussion

➤ Characteristics of respondents (age, gender, education and occupation) satisfaction index for Indonesian Health Card users in hospital services

From the research results, it can be interpreted that the characteristics of respondents who use Indonesian Health Cards are that the majority are 80.7% early adults, 26-35 years old, the majority gender is 74.7% female, and the majority have a high school education, 76.7%, while for occupation the majority is 70. % self-employed.

Gender is a biological difference between men and women related to reproductive organs and their functions (Azisah, 2016). Education is the process of changing the attitudes and behavior of a person or group of people so that they become adults through teaching and training, operational processes and educational methods (Hidayat, 2019). Everyone experiences aging, but each person's aging is different, depending on hereditary factors, environmental stressors, and many other factors (Stanley, 2006).

This is in line with the results of Endartiwi's research (2020) where the gender of 58% were mostly female, age 67% \leq 55 years old, the highest education was 52% high school level and the highest occupation was 31% of respondents working in Farmers/Laborers. Oemar (2017) gender 71% female, age 50% $>$ 20 years, occupation civil servant/civil servant.

From the results of the research, theory and related research, the researcher assumes that the characteristics of female respondents are the highest because they are identical, women are more sensitive to feeling the touch of the services provided because women prioritize feelings, whereas in high school education and above the majority are at this level of education. They can already differentiate between hope and reality and most of them are at an early age because at this age people are good at analyzing and intervening in every action they feel.

➤ *Know the description of the quality index per element of service for patients using Indonesian Health Cards regarding services in hospital inpatient installations*

The results of the analysis show that of all inpatient service elements, the lowest average value per service element is the speed of service, 2.44, which is perceived as poor by patients using Indonesian Health Cards. The highest element was 2.84, namely the element of service procedures felt by patients with good performance.

Hope is the most important key for any healthcare provider who cares about patient or customer satisfaction. According to Rangkut, hope is the level of customer interest, namely the customer's confidence before trying or buying a product or service, which is used as a reference standard in assessing a product or service (Syafudin, 2011). Adherence to professional standards of health services by using available resources to meet all client needs and optimal health goals (Bustami, 2011), according to Nasution (2015) is a comparison of the quality of health services. the goods or services offered are by the desires, needs and expectations of customers.

In line with Susana's (2023) research results, the highest average score was 88.75 for the service procedure element which was perceived by patients as very good and for the facility and infrastructure element 2.68 with the perception of good service. This is not in line with Endartiwi's research (2020) where the lowest average score was 2.94 for the service procedure element and the highest was 3.12 for the service security element. Dzulfadli (2020) where the lowest average value was 2.97 for the service time

element while the highest was 3.85 for handling complaints, facilities and input. Wahdania (2015) where the average value is 1.78 for the service environment comfort element with poor service unit performance, while the highest average value for the service procedure element is 3.69 with "very good" service performance.

Oemar (2017) stated that the lowest average score for officers was 2.46 for the element of speed of service for officers, while the highest score was 3.14 for the element of ease of service procedures. Heriyanto (2016) where the lowest average value for the element is speed of service, 2.96, while the highest value is for the element of service cost certainty, 3.21. Sukanti (2015) found that the lowest average element value was 3.13 for the element of the suitability of service requirements and the highest average value was 3.49 for politeness and friendliness of the officers.

From the results of research and theory and related research, researchers assume that someone will feel satisfied and say they have good performance when they come for treatment at the health service, the service does not take long to wait, the staff serves quickly, is friendly, according to schedule and so on. Of course, this will have an impact on the company being valued by customers as being able to provide the best and highest quality service and causing customers to come back.

➤ *Know the description of the patient satisfaction index for Indonesian Health Card users regarding the performance of hospital inpatient installation services*

The results of the analysis of the weighted average value were converted to see the patient satisfaction index for Indonesian Health Card users in inpatient settings with an index of 62.75, this indicates that the performance of nursing services is good with quality B (Good).

Quality of health services is health services that can satisfy every user of health services by the average level of satisfaction of the population (Syafudin, 2011). Satisfaction is the level of a person's feelings after comparing the performance/results they feel with their expectations (Supranto, 2008). According to the State Minister for State Apparatus Empowerment (MENPAN) (2004), data and information regarding the level of community satisfaction is obtained from the results of quantitative and qualitative measurements of community opinion in the procurement of services, comparing community expectations and needs. public service providers.

The research results are in line with Susana's (2023) research, the satisfaction index value is 3.06, whereas the service quality index value has a performance predicate of "Good". Endartiwi's (2020) community satisfaction index with an index of 76.18 shows the quality of service performance is in the "good" category. Dzulfadli (2020) stated that the community satisfaction index was 80.78, where the quality score was B with the health service performance being "Good". Wahdania's (2015) community satisfaction index value of 68.93 is included in the service quality "Good".

In line with Oemar (2017), the satisfaction index is 68.25, which shows good service quality performance. Heriyanto (2016) obtained a community satisfaction index of 76.80 where service performance was good with service quality. B. Sukamti's (2015) community satisfaction index was 81.74, and service performance was very good. Prakoeswa (2023) where the community satisfaction index in service performance is 80.14 with good service quality. Armiati (2022), the index value of community satisfaction with health services is 84.81 in service units, including "very good" health services.

Based on research, theory and related research, researchers think that everyone wants to be served well, greeted with a smile, and friendly, so that will automatically create pleasant service felt by customers, this proves that when customers receive good service it will certainly increase the index individual satisfaction for both patients using health services and their families.

IV. CONCLUSION

The conclusions in this study discuss the patient satisfaction index for Indonesian Health Card users in hospital services as follows:

- Characteristics of respondents who use the Indonesian Health Card, age 80.7%, early adults 26-35 years, gender 74.7% female, 76.7% have a high school education, while for work 70% are self-employed.
- Of all the elements of inpatient services, the lowest average value is 2.44 for the speed of service element and the highest is 2.84 for the service procedure element.
- From the average value per converted element there is an index of 62.75, thus the service performance is of good quality.

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